

ISic2862

I.Sicily inscription 2862

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local, from Fuardo)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 13796

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334491

1. Διωγένης²⁶ Διογένης²⁶
2. Πανφίλας.
- 3.
4. ΑΠ
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645256

PHI 334491

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2862. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387547>